

WAERMER Waermewende im urbanen Gebäudebestand mit Hilfe interaktiver Entscheidungsraumanalyse

**Model Validation Workshop:
Concept and Results**

Deliverable 5.2

January 2025

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Gefördert durch:

aufgrund eines Beschlusses
des Deutschen Bundestages

**Das Projekt wird gefördert vom Bundesministerium für
Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK)
unter dem Förderkennzeichen 03EI5235A.**

Project acronym: **WAERMER**
 Project title: **Waermewende im urbanen
Gebäudebestand mit Hilfe interaktiver
Entscheidungsraumanalyse**

Start of Project: 1th August 2022
 Duration: 36 Month
 Project coordinator: Universität Kassel
 Project website: <https://www.uni-kassel.de/go/waermer>

Report title: Model Validation Workshop: Concept and Results
 Deliverable: D5.2
 Kind of Deliverable: report
 Dissemination level: public

Responsible AP: AP4
 Responsible Partner: Uni Kassel, FG Integrierte Energiesysteme

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.16792148

Date: January 2025

Version history:

<i>Version</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>Datum</i>	<i>Autor(en)</i>
0.1	Draft	23.01.2025	Sascha Holzhauer
0.9	For review	11.08.2025	Sascha Holzhauer
1.0	Final	08.01.2026	Sascha Holzhauer

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1 Summary

As part of the research project WAERMER, a workshop to validate the agent-based model AHOIS was conducted with stakeholders of the project in December 2024. This report contains a literature review on stakeholder validation of agent-based models, the workshop concept, the main results from the workshop as well as participants' feedback. It discusses consequences for further model development and reflects the appropriateness of the workshop concept in the given context.

The model validation was structured into four parts: model assumptions, theories, processes; model behaviour and dynamics; possible interventions and model outcomes; and possible model extensions. The participants' feedback was overall positive. Suggestions for improvements include particular visualisations as well as building subgroups for validation of specific model parts.

2 Introduction

This deliverable preserves the concepts and results of the model validation workshop held on 5th December 2024 online via MS[®] Teams. The main objective was the validation and further development of the agent-based model AHOIS (Agent-based homeowners investments in stages) which is deployed in the research project WAERMER. The purpose of AHOIS is to simulate heating related investment decisions of private building owners as decentral actors in order to identify interventions that allow the achievement of defined sustainable district targets (Digel et al., 2024).

Stakeholders, especially those that apply the model or use its results, demand credibility of the model: the model needs to address its purpose. "Validation is defined as the process of determining if a model adequately represents the system under study for the model's intended purpose" (Collins et al., 2024). The validation comprises especially the behaviour of represented actors (building owners, plumbers, energy advisors) but also system level dynamics such as the uptake of innovative heating technologies.

Besides validating the model, the workshop also pursues the objective to familiarise stakeholders who did not engage in the model development with underlying assumptions of the model. To this end, the objective was to check model comprehension, i.e. testing whether the audience of model results, namely the stakeholders of the municipal heat planning process, understands and finally trusts the agent-based model and its outputs. Therefore, the purpose was also to check plausibility, transparency and intelligibility of model assumptions and outcomes.

3 Literature Review

To successfully apply an (agent-based) model to policy support, i.e. to use the model to derive recommendations for interventions that support a defined desired target scenario, model credibility is key. Unless responsible representatives do trust the model, they are unlikely to consider model results in their decision making.

According to Belfrage et al. (2024), credibility is defined as "a measure of confidence in the model's inferential capability". Inferential capability in turn requires causal inference of units, treatments, outcomes, and settings from the model to the target system. Only then insights from the model can be mapped to the target system. Therefore, it is a good idea to validate the relationships between

agents and actors, modelled interventions and their real-world counterparts, model outcomes and expected real-world effects, and applied parameters and their empirical base.

Often, the process of model development is considered as a joint venture between modellers who have modelling and programming skills and domain experts. Agent-based modelling is seen as a user-driven approach where domain experts request model features and require user-friendly tools to validate the model (Tack et al., 2023). In many cases though, as in the project WAERMER, modellers obtain domain knowledge by literature research, project meetings and further consultation with stakeholders and experts. Nevertheless, it is strongly recommended to play back the model concept and implementation explicitly to domain experts to ensure model validity.

There is a considerable body of model validation techniques for agent-based modelling, especially as agent-based models seek to map actors' relevant behaviour as observed in the real world. When choosing validation techniques for a validation workshop it is important that stakeholders accept and understand the methods (Collins et al., 2024).

For the workshop, given the experience and expertise of involved stakeholders, we find visualisation techniques, causal analysis, and face validity most appropriate. "Visualizations connect model users to simulation runs by providing relatable and intuitive representations of simulation events, behaviors, and statistical indicators. [...] Visual techniques have high value in facilitating insights as they can be tailored based on the intended user audience, message, and model context" (Collins et al., 2024). Causal analyses are especially suitable to track agents' decision-making and identify the reasons why agents invest in deprecated heating technologies instead of desired alternatives in case they do (see Figure 3). Face validity is a low-threshold method to leverage stakeholders' expertise in building owners but also plumbers' and energy advisors' behaviour.

Regarding validation workshops, these should involve diverse stakeholders including model developers, domain experts, and end-users. End-users such as policy makers should check whether the model fulfils their expectations and is credible, domain experts evaluate the validity of represented entities and processes, and model developers derive required changes to the model and discuss their realizability. Various workshop formats have been elaborated and conducted, e.g. a role-playing-game for a dairy supply chain model (Utomo et al., 2022) or a participatory simulation gaming approach for validation of a city logistics model (Anand et al., 2016).

4 Workshop Concept

4.1 Participants

Considering the workshop's purpose, several stakeholders of the local heat provision planning process in Kiel-Oppendorf were invited and took part in the online meeting (see Literature Review):

- House owners from Oppendorf
- Grid operator

- Energy Advisers
- WAERMER: Universität Kassel (AP2)
- WAERMER: Fraunhofer IEE (AP3)
- WAERMER: LH Kiel

Unfortunately, despite intensive advertising and tailoring the agenda to their needs (asking them to join the first hour only), installers did not accept the invitation.

After registration, participants obtained further information about the research project, the agent-based model, the purpose of the workshop, and the agenda via email (see Annex B – Infos zum Modellvalidierungs-Workshop im Projekt WAERMER (Stakeholder briefing)).

4.2 Invitation

The initial invitation addressed the stakeholder by name, presented the purpose of the research project WAERMER, how the stakeholder is connected to it, and described the agent-based model and its objectives. Then, the workshops agenda was sketched, and the role of the stakeholder was mentioned. Contact details for further inquiries were given, and a request to respond.

“Sehr geehrter <Stakeholder>,

im Rahmen des Forschungsprojektes WAERMER, in dem die Landeshauptstadt Kiel gemeinsam mit der Uni Kassel und dem Fraunhofer Institut für Energiewirtschaft und Energiesystemtechnik die Faktoren für das Gelingen der Wärmewende untersucht, hatten Sie bereits vor einiger Zeit an einem Telefoninterview teilgenommen, wofür wir sehr dankbar sind.

In Projekt kommt ein sogenanntes agentenbasiertes Modell zum Einsatz, das die Investitionsentscheidungen privater Gebäudebesitzer*innen in einem Quartier abbildet. Die Entscheidungen der Eigentümer*innen werden dabei beeinflusst von Faktoren wie der Verfügbarkeit von Informationen, Investitionssummen für verschiedene Heiztechnologien, individuellen Präferenzen, aber auch der Interaktion mit Installateuren und Energieberatern. Ziel ist es, mit dem Modell die Entscheidungen der Anwohner*innen bezüglich ihrer zukünftigen Heiztechnologie über ein ganzes Quartier realitätsnah zu simulieren, um Maßnahmen zur Beschleunigung der Wärmewende zu testen.

Um das Modell zu prüfen, möchten wir Sie als Experten ganz herzlich am Donnerstag, den 5.12. ab 9.00 Uhr zu einem Online-Workshop einladen. Dort werden wir das Modell vorstellen und es mit Ihnen gemeinsam auf die Gültigkeit der Annahmen und die abgebildeten Prozesse hin überprüfen. Außerdem können wir mit Ihrer Hilfe auch noch wichtige Erweiterungen in das Modell einbauen. Wir freuen uns deshalb sehr, wenn Sie sich Zeit für diesen Austausch nehmen. Insgesamt ist der Workshop bis 12 Uhr geplant. Wir sind uns aber bewusst, dass diese Zeitspanne insbesondere für Sie als Installateur schwer zu realisieren ist und konzipieren das Programm daher so, dass Ihre Teilnahme bereits ab einer Stunde gewinnbringend ist.

Nachfragen zu dem Termin richten Sie bitte an Dr. Sascha Holzhauer (Sascha.Holzhauer@uni-kassel.de, +49 561 804-6513). Eine Rückmeldung zu Ihrer Teilnahme bis 2. Dezember an Sascha

Holzhauser würde uns bei der Organisation der Veranstaltung sehr helfen. Weitere Informationen zur Teilnahme folgen dann. Im Anhang finden Sie den Termin auch nochmal als Outlook-Termin mit einem entsprechenden Einwahllink zur Videokonferenz.”

4.3 Agenda

To familiarise the participants with the basic subject of validation, they were initially introduced to agent-based modelling. A focus was on the art of modelling to represent only the essential entities and processes in the model. After all, the evaluation should consider that the best model is not the one that depicts reality as accurately as possible, but the one that is also limited to the relevant processes and thus makes them more accessible for analysis.

We continued with a presentation of potential heating options and their attributes as subjects of agents' decision making, followed by the representation of agents themselves. Then, validation followed in parts 1 to 3, complemented with the discussion of model extensions in part 4. These parts are addressed in detail in subsequent sections.

9:00 Check-in and Welcome

Introduction to agent-based modelling

Part 1: Assumptions, theories, processes (50 minutes)

Part 2: Model behaviour and dynamics (40 minutes)

10:30 Break (20 minutes)

Part 3: Possible interventions and outcomes: heat pumps, pellets (40 minutes)

Part 4: Possible Model extensions (30 minutes)

12:00 Feedback and Check-out

Besides a structured moderation of the entire workshop, taking minutes of the whole discussion is crucial to identify relevant statements and derive required consequence for further model development.

4.4 Part 1: Assumptions, theories, processes

During part 1 the workshop iterated through several of most relevant processes, considering underlying assumptions and theories:

- Assumptions
 - Bounded rationality (satisficing) in decision-making
 - Imperfect information
 - Social influence
 - Budget constraints

- Availability of technologies
- Underlying theories
 - Bamberg's stage theory
 - Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

After the presentation of the process, usually with the help of flow charts, listings and tables (see annex A for the entire set of presented slides), participants were able to ask questions regarding their understanding of the process. We then discussed plausibility of assumptions, behaviour and parameter values. Finally, alternative representations were considered and compared with the implemented approach.

4.5 Part 2: Model behaviour and dynamics

During the second part, the focus was on specific model results to validate model behaviour and dynamics at the macro level. To interpret the model results better, input data to the model (building data, milieu data), aggregate properties of the agent population (income distribution), and heating systems (age distribution, shares of initial technologies) were presented. These model results were inspected:

- Heating system adoption patterns
- Heating system replacement patterns
- Information source use
- Affordability dynamics
- Intermediary queues

Relevant figures to view these results were:

- Heat system distribution among agents (area diagram, see Figure 1)
- Number of replacements (time series)
- Share of deciding agents (time series)
- Scenario fulfilment (time series, see Figure 2)
- Number of triggers (bar chart)
- Average system age (time series)

Figure 1: Shares of installed heating systems over time

Figure 2: Fulfilment of targets for four different scenarios

4.6 Part 3: Possible interventions and outcomes

The objective of part 3 was checking proposed interventions for plausibility and brainstorm new ones, including plausible combinations of interventions. Parameter ranges for interventions were discussed. The list of considered interventions comprises:

- Installation price manipulation: subsidies and direct changes
- Fuel cost manipulation
- Plumber training
- Energy advisor consultations
- Information campaigns: spreading knowledge and triggers

These annotated figures were shown to highlight the effects of interventions compared to the baseline scenario:

- Scenario fulfilment (time series, see Figure 2)
- Succeeding agents per decision stage to identify barriers (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Number of agents who succeeded in the decision stage towards heat pumps during the five-year-periods.

4.7 Part 4: Model expansions

The objective of this part is to discuss strength and weaknesses, and form expectations and make proposals for extensions to the model. To think about pros and cons of the agent-based model the figure of influence factors to the agents' decision making (see Figure 4) as well as the input- and output figure was presented. Suggestions for model extensions to be discussed are:

- Propagation
- Uncertainty preferences
- Alternative payment schemes

Figure 4: Influence factors to the agents' investment decision making.

The discussion about possible extensions can be facilitated by presenting a list of model components:

- Triggers
- Information search
- Planning / Evaluation of options
- Installation
- Plumber training
- Energy consultation
- Agent-Agent interactions

5 Results

5.1 Feedback towards the agent-based model

In the following we list relevant outcomes from the validation workshop (noted in the minutes) to give an impression of the importance of conducting the validation event. In the discussion (see section 6.1) we discuss the consequences for further model development.

5.1.1 Part 1: Assumptions, theories, processes

- Many buildings owners act because they are afraid.
- More effort is required in modelling the course of actions, also in a valid temporal representation as e.g. changes of legislation and according expectations of house owners is important.
- Consider anticipation of prohibitions of certain heat technologies in near future (leads to increased investment in prohibited technologies of certain milieus).

- Long waiting times (for plumber and/or infrastructure) cause investments in alternative solutions for some milieus.

5.1.2 Part 2: Model behaviour and dynamics

- Performance of some scenarios due to specific input parameters was questioned. We therefore obtained hints on which input data needs to be checked (efficiency, costs).
- Autarchy was requested as additional preference for building owners.
- Price developments (energy prices, CO₂ prices) need to be considered.
- Stakeholders confirm low shares of pellet heating.
- Social network relations have a significant impact on investment decisions.

5.1.3 Part 3: Possible interventions and outcomes

- The share of granted subsidies is too low.
- From stakeholders we obtained the information that energy advisors are not mandatory to apply for subsidies (apart from additional 5% bonus in case of an integrated refurbishment plan).
- Stakeholders confirmed the dependence of decision makers from plumbers (first contact).

5.2 Participants' acceptance and trust in the model

We asked participants to evaluate the correctness of assumptions in the model (see Figure 5).

Bewerten Sie die Richtigkeit der Annahmen des Modells:

8 Antworten

Figure 5: Evaluation of model assumptions' correctness

We asked participants to state their trust in model results (Figure 6).

Bewerten Sie das Vertrauen in die Modellergebnisse in der aktuellen Form:

8 Antworten

Figure 6: Trust in model results of the current version

5.3 Feedback from Participants to the workshop format

We asked participants to evaluate the workshop to learn lessons for future model evaluation events. Very satisfied were participants with the selection of content for the validation workshop (Figure 7).

Bewerten Sie die angesprochenen Inhalte des Workshops:

8 Antworten

Figure 7: Evaluation of workshop content.

Similarly, all attended persons perceived the duration of the workshop as appropriate (orange: The workshop duration was appropriate; red: The workshop was somewhat too short to consider all interesting topics) – see Figure 8.

Bewerten Sie bitte den Zeitrahmen des Workshops:

8 Antworten

Figure 8: Evaluation of workshop duration.

Seven out of eight participants gave more detailed answers telling which parts they felt too short (Figure 9). Whereas the introduction and model dynamics were perceived as “appropriate” (orange), parts 3 (interventions) and part 4 (model extensions) were found somewhat too short (red) by some.

Wenn Sie mögen, bewerten Sie bitte den Umfang der einzelnen Teile des Workshops:

Figure 9: Evaluation of workshop parts' duration.

This corresponds to the rating of each part's presentation of content (Figure 10). All persons who answered the question found the presentations comprehensible. Four out of six persons found introduction and model dynamics also exciting, five out of six found the part about interventions exciting.

Wenn Sie mögen, bewerten Sie bitte die Präsentation der Inhalte der einzelnen Teile des Workshops:

Figure 10: Evaluation of presented content per workshop part.

Finally, 7 out of 8 participants agreed to take part in another workshop to validate the model (blue), and one participant stated "maybe" (red) (Figure 11).

Wären Sie bereit, an einem weiteren Workshop zur Validierung des Modells teilzunehmen?

8 Antworten

Figure 11: Willingness to participate in another validation workshop.

6 Discussion

6.1 Conclusions for AHOIS

An important outcome of the workshop are demands on the model that are to be implemented before applying AHOIS to perform simulations for the second decision workshop. We therefore list here changes to the model that were requested during discussions during the workshop.

- Enable building owners to switch selected heating technology in case they face too long waiting times.
- Reflect uncertainty with respect to continuation of subsidies in increased number of earlier investments.
- Consider autarchy as an additional preference building owners consider in their decision making.
- Consider price developments for energy and CO₂.
- Correct the false dependence of subsidies from energy advise.
- Implement social influence via social networks and neighbours.

6.2 Suitability of Agenda

Since the overall workshop time was limited, we could not afford to present the agent-based model in detail. Therefore, we focused on the purpose of modelling in general and within the WAERMER project in particular. The basic idea was to frame participants not to ask for more details to represent in the model but to judge represented processes with the purpose of investigating impacts on investment decisions in mind (compare Occam's razor – the intention to cut out all unnecessary details from the model). However, to understand the limits and opportunities of agent-based modelling, participants were introduced to a few basic concepts such as agent's autonomy, their goal-oriented action, bounded rationality, and interaction processes between individual agents.

We were then able to pass over to the first discussion part about assumptions, theories, and processes rather smoothly, explaining relevant agents and processes with sufficient detail. We asked stakeholders explicitly to evaluate the agents in the model who represent their own role, as experts accordingly.

The second part about model behaviour and dynamics was utilised to present results of simulations. The focus was now on the plausibility of results in a qualitative way. Participants were asked to check whether they miss relevant dynamics or have a feeling that important drivers are not reflected in model dynamics. During this part it is important to highlight the aspired degree of detail in model results. Especially as we also show spatial distributions of e.g. heat systems on building levels, participants might be tempted to compare specific buildings of the simulation with their real world counterpart. Therefore, it is important to note that accuracy can only be maintained on a mesa level, e.g. building blocks, but single buildings will necessarily deviate from the real world, e.g. because of reasons of data privacy.

In general, participants' feedback encourages to extend the validation workshop slightly to discuss the modelling of interventions longer and elaborate more on possible model extensions.

6.3 Suggestions for Presenting Results

Figure 12 is a valuable figure as it shows the obstacles house owners face during their decision for a new heat system. Many agents get triggered, about half of them are unsatisfied with their current system and seek to replace it. At least after 2030 almost all agents know about heat pumps, but many represented house owners cannot finance the kind of new heating system (gap between green and red bars). Furthermore, a considerable share of agents favours a different heating system during

preference-based evaluation. To compare the four time spans even better, a percental representation (how many percent of all agents are triggered, how many percent of triggered agents are unsatisfied and so on) would be more suitable.

Figure 12 Obstacle for adoption of heat pumps during time spans

6.4 Discussion of the overall workshop concept

Given the positive feedback of stakeholders regarding time and content, the overall format can be evaluated positive. Future concepts should further consider several validation workshops during the (iterative) model development instead of a single one. Since the model usually gets updated after corrections and extension requests, also validation should react to changes to the model, also to update stakeholders and keep credibility (Balci, 1998).

7 Literature

- Anand, N., Meijer, D., van Duin, J., Tavasszy, L., & Meijer, S. (2016). Validation of an agent based model using a participatory simulation gaming approach: The case of city logistics. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 71, 489–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2016.08.002>
- Balci, O. (1998). Verification, Validation, and Testing. In J. Banks (Ed.), *Handbook of Simulation* (pp. 335–393). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470172445.ch10>
- Belfrage, M., Johansson, E., Lorig, F., & Davidsson, P. (2024) [In]Credible Models – Verification, Validation & Accreditation of Agent-Based Models to Support Policy-Making. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 27(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.18564/jasss.5505>

- Collins, A., Koehler, M., & Lynch, C. (2024). Methods That Support the Validation of Agent-Based Models: An Overview and Discussion. *Journal of Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*, 27(1), Article 11. <https://doi.org/10.18564/jasss.5258>
- Digel, I., Holzhauser, S., & Krebs, F. (2024). Exploring Investment Decisions in Home Heating System Replacement with a Multi-stage Algorithm: An Agent-Based Model. In C. Elsenbroich & H. Verhagen (Eds.), *Advances in Social Simulation* (pp. 137–149). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-57785-7_12
- Tack, E., Énée, G., Gaillard, T., Fotsing, J.-M., & Flouvat, F. (2023). Towards User-Centred Validation and Calibration of Agent-Based Models. In *15th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence*. Symposium conducted at the meeting of SCITEPRESS-Science and Technology Publications.
- Utomo, D. S., Onggo, B. S. S., Eldridge, S., Daud, A. R., & Tejaningsih, S. (2022). Eliciting agents' behaviour and model validation using role playing game in agent-based dairy supply chain model. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 73(12), 2670–2693. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01605682.2021.2013137>

8 Annex A – Agentenbasierte Simulation: Validierungsworkshop (Slides)

Deliverable	5.2 (Annex A)
Kind of Deliverable	Slides
Title	Agentenbasierte Simulation: Validierungsworkshop
Responsible WP	AP 4
Responsible Partner	FG INES / Uni Kassel
Publication level	Public
Language	German
Date	09.04.2025
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15225907

9 Annex B – Infos zum Modellvalidierungs-Workshop im Projekt WAERMER (Stakeholder briefing)

Deliverable	5.2 (Annex B)
Kind of Deliverable	PDF
Title	Infos zum Modellvalidierungs-Workshop im Projekt WAERMER
Responsible WP	AP 4
Responsible Partner	FG INES / Uni Kassel
Publication level	Public
Language	German
Date	05.12.2024
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.16792552